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Lived Experiences of Non-SpED Teachers in Inclusive Education

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Abstract

This phenomenological inquiry sought to delve into the lived experiences of non-SPED teachers handling diagnosed SPED students in an inclusive classroom in selected elementary schools in Antipolo during the school year 2023–2024. Based on the transcribed responses, the following overarching themes evolve: a) Prominent and Recurring Needs in Inclusive Classrooms; b.) Subjective Experiences with Support, Training, and Resources; c.) Personal and Emotional Experiences of Non-SPED Teachers; and d.) Adaptation of Teaching Methods, Classroom Management, and Collaboration. In addition, some positive experiences that non-SPED can have with administrators include routine principal interaction, progress monitoring, and structured professional development activities. Still, some teachers see a lack of administrative support. Moreover, Personal and emotional accounts of non-SPED teachers revealed that working in inclusive classes is not an easy task. It may involve frequent emotions such as anger, frustration, and patience. Personal initiative includes giving resources, taking part in trainings or conferences, and changing one's style of teaching based on the individual characteristics of diagnosed pupils. To this end, non-SPED teachers use inclusion treatment approach, set rules, provide for safety of learners, and consider environmental issues that can influence on their classroom management. Collaboration among colleagues include the provision of open communication, sharing of ideas, orientation of colleges on incorporation of special education practices to cater for diagnosed students.

Keywords: *non-SpED teachers, phenomenology, inclusive education*

Introduction

Everyone who wants to learn should be able to attend school because education is so important to every Filipino (Philippine Const, Article XIV, 1987). This is true regardless of sex, age, gender, religion, creed, socioeconomic status, social or ethnic origin, political or other affiliation, and physical or mental condition. The term "inclusion" has been often used in connection with education since many years ago.

Ainscow (2020) stipulated that inclusive education - in its broadest sense - is a fundamental human right principle supporting diversity and emphasizing equity and fairness to meet students' various needs. While inclusive education is still seen in some countries as a strategy for serving students with disabilities in the mainstream educational setting (physical placement).

Likewise, school administrators are accountable to the students as required by RA 9155 and other relevant criteria that are rooted in the DepEd's vision and goal. According to their potential, and abilities, they should acquire the knowledge, skills, and values that are necessary for their overall growth. Considering the roles and responsibilities for the welfare of our student populations, particularly those who are less privileged in terms of the intellectual, physical, social, and environmental elements that affect their development. Education should be available to everyone, including individuals with physical and intellectual disabilities who must be present in a setting free from bullying and fears.

Relatively, Republic Act No. 10533 makes it abundantly plain; else Section 5 of the 2013 Enhanced Basic Education Act promotes the inclusion of all students in improved basic education by putting in place programs that cater to their physical, intellectual, psychological, and cultural requirements. learners. This demonstrates how crucial mainstreaming is to the youngsters with special needs who attend regular classes. Employees must be aware of their roles in placing greater emphasis on inclusiveness.

Moreover, the education of learners with special needs has come a long way; from special education (SPED) to integrated education, and from integrated education to inclusive education, it has undergone many changes.

However, SPED is currently a hot topic that is extensively debated in the field of education, including the Philippines. It has consistently been referred to as a new educational paradigm and as an educational reform objective to create inclusive societies as part of the global education for all agenda. The same is acknowledged in the Philippines, although while having laws and legal framework that support education for all, especially in the implementation of SPED classes, the aspect of education for all is not adequately implemented.

Consequently, as noted in the DepEd Order No. 044, s. 2021, The Policy Guidelines on the Provision of Educational Programs and Services for Learners with Disabilities in the K–12 Basic Education Program was issued by former DepEd Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones. This policy serves as a guide for external stakeholders and partners in addressing the needs of learners with disabilities. It was issued with the aim of providing an overall direction and guidance in the organization, management, and implementation of appropriate programs, services, and interventions for learners with disabilities at the different levels of governance in the Department of Education (DepEd).

The general education teacher shall serve as Receiving Teachers in the general education classroom for learners with disabilities. They shall collaborate with SPED teachers, non-teaching personnel and/ or parents. Inclusive Learning Resource Centers (ILRC) Coordinator and/ or Resource Room Teachers and other professionals in responding to specific and additional needs of learners with disabilities for their success in learning the k to 12 Curriculum.

Given all the above information, it is crucial to understand the various difficulties that the SPED teachers encounter when managing their classes. The researcher, who has been teaching in Special Education for about seven years, pursued this study to address the topic of learners with special learning needs by investigating the challenges and difficulties of receiving SPED teachers experience when teaching learners with learning difficulties and how they attempt to overcome these situations.

As a result, this study addresses the topic of learners with special learning needs by investigating the challenges and difficulties of receiving SPED teachers experience when teaching learners with learning difficulties and how they attempt to overcome these situations. Thus, the Schools Division Office – Antipolo have been numerous issues with teaching learners who have learning disabilities. Most of the elementary teachers in the division have moderate knowledge and skills and less training to provide special education for these learners with learning disabilities.

Research Questions

This phenomenological inquiry sought to delve into the lived experiences of non-SPED teachers handling diagnosed SPED students in an inclusive classroom in selected elementary schools in Antipolo during the school year 2023–2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. What are the most prominent and recurring needs expressed by non-SPED teachers as they teach students with special needs in inclusive classroom settings?
2. How do non-SPED teachers subjectively experience the support, training, and resources provided to them in addressing the needs of diagnosed students within inclusive classrooms?
3. What personal and emotional experiences do non-SPED teachers encounter when working with diagnosed students?
4. In what ways do non-SPED teachers adapt their teaching methods, classroom management, and collaboration with other educators to better meet the unique needs of diagnosed students?
5. What training program for Non-SPED teachers and inclusive education may be proposed resulting from this study?

Literature Review

According to Block et. al. (2019), a type of education called special education focuses on the requirements of children with impairments and learning difficulties. With inclusion at its core, special education has changed significantly over the past 50 years as a result of ground-breaking laws and regulations that were put into place.

In addition, Quinones (2022) claimed that inclusive education (IE) is one of the trends in special education that it allows learners with special needs (LSN) to participate regularly in a classroom and be supported to learn, contribute, participate, and respond to the curriculum and instruction. The approach provides a balance of opportunities for both LSN and regular classmates with equal opportunities and experiences. Inclusive education supports the educational needs of special people and allows their inclusion in the normal learning environment. On the other hand, the integration of LSN with students from various diverse backgrounds, and the teachers, poses a great challenge.

More so, according to Nuñez and Rosales (2021), an increasing student population created the chance to embrace diversity in the classroom, which led to the implementation of "inclusive education" (IE) in many regions of the world. Nevertheless, despite the diversity, talents, and disabilities present in the classroom, both teachers and students shared the desire to learn as their main educational objective. As a result, educational institutions have committed to putting in place programs that will meet the needs of every learner, regardless of his or her talents or limitations. Studies on the effective implementation of inclusive education have primarily been undertaken in Middle Eastern nations, while there has been little research on this topic in the Philippines.

Moreover, UNICEF (2018), developing countries including the Philippines are suffering from poor quality teacher training and inadequate classroom facilities. Given the distance learning, it adds a level of difficulty to the preparedness of regular teachers in handling inclusive education. Teachers were challenged and encountered complexity in teaching. In addition to this, schools and SPED centers are ill equipped to practice inclusive education, and it will be difficult for the students as well as the regular teachers.

Meanwhile, Aquino et. al. (2019) aimed to find out the lived experiences of the 7 teachers of a special education center handling special learners. Some of the participants described their experience as a roller coaster ride experience for it is a combination of positive and negative experiences. Other participants revealed that teaching special learners was a challenging yet very fulfilling and overwhelming experience for them after seeing their learners progressed and succeed. Some participants revealed that they cannot communicate well with the special children because they do not have the knowledge to do the sign language.

Furthermore, Sampaga (2020) concerned with the lived experiences of special education teachers in San Fernando City SPED Integrated School. The findings from this study are that novice special education teachers' exposure to mentoring varies and there is a

need for mentoring programs that are specifically targeted to novice special education teachers. The results of this study revealed that the novice special education teacher participants felt confident in teaching students with disabilities. Participants also felt that mentoring was an important form of support and revealed that they intended to remain in the teaching profession, teaching students with disabilities.

Quizana and Espiritu (2023) ascertained the challenges encountered and coping strategies used by teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program in public elementary schools of the third congressional district in the division of Quezon. It is revealed in the study that learners with Autism Spectrum Disorders, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), and Dyslexia are the major types of learners with special educational needs that are handled by teachers in SPED inclusive education program. The common teaching strategies that teachers use when they instructing learners are the following: using visual aids, educational videos, positive reinforcement, simplification of the lesson, consistent routines, peer tutoring, giving clear instructions, giving written handouts, reading materials, repeated instructions, giving multiple examples, using individualized learning instructions, cooperative and experimental learning.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a phenomenological research design, which is a philosophy derived from phenomenology. Phenomenology has also been described as a philosophy which can help underpin qualitative research (Fleming et al. 2003). This study aimed at finding out the difficult situations in life that come because learners with special needs may enrolled into non-SPED teachers' classroom.

Participants

This involved ten non-SPED teachers teaching and managing SPED students within an inclusive setting at the elementary level. All of them did not have a specialization in Special Education in their college degree. This sample size was purposive, aimed at depth and richness in the examination of the lived realities of non-SPED teachers. Therefore, this study was done using in-depth interviews with individuals from a relatively small sample population to have an in-depth knowledge of the personal experiences within the context of inclusive education.

Instrument

An interview guide which was designed purposively was used as a data collection instrument to obtain quality information to explain how non-specialized educators worked in inclusive classes with students who had been already identified for SPED. Using this interview guide, meaningful interaction was established between them, and participants were given an opportunity to freely express their opinions and feelings without feeling restricted or bound.

The interview guide was validated by experts in the field of inclusive education and qualitative research prior to being applied. The consulted experts included division and district supervisors, school principals, experienced SPED teachers who had much expertise regarding special education and inclusion, scrutinized the clarity, relevance, and adequacy of the interview guide regarding items in the interview guide. This helped them in modifying and improving the interview guide to capture the complexities involved in the experiences of non-SPED teachers.

Procedure

This study followed the systematic and ethical process in collecting relevant and valid data. In fact, approval was asked from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) of the Division of Antipolo City, and the SDS's letter and approval were given to administer the questionnaire to undertake the study. Next, the researcher formally requested permission from the principals of the chosen elementary schools for the in-depth interview. A copy of the authorized letter from the Schools Division Office was attached to the request, further emphasizing the authenticity and approval of the research.

The researcher allowed flexibility and convenience in the data gathering process for the intended research informants, who are elementary school teachers. The researcher arranged meetings with the participants that they were most available for. The researcher carried out member checking, which involved returning the data that was to be analyzed to the participants themselves, for them to check the validity of interpretations. Peer debriefing was also implemented, where other SPED teachers reviewed the diverse elements of the research design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical issues greatly contributed to the study of the lived experiences of the non-SPED teachers in the inclusive classes. Informed consent has also been adhered to during the research by providing elaborate information on the objectives of the study and procedures. The participants were also assured of their voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any stage without consequences. These included coding techniques during data analysis which preserved the non-SPED teacher's privacy and replaced identifying information pseudonyms.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Overarching Theme One. Prominent and Recurring Needs in Inclusive Classrooms

A. Training and Support

Non-SPED teacher training and support is the thrust of the “Training and Support” theme. As shown in quotation 1 (informant 1) training needs are highlighted concerning the need to include learners with special needs and shows sensitivity about prevailing expertise deficit. The second quotation (informant no. 6) further expounds this point of view, highlighting the need for constant teacher training in order to deal with children having special needs as well as on individualized learning plan for mainstream inclusion. The attendance of seminars, quoted under quotation 1 and 2 (Informant 5 and 6) represents an active strategy for qualitative development, paying special attention to certain aspects such as the sign language illustrates the intention of covering different forms of conversation. However, seminars under Administration Support are recognized (Quotation informant 8) yet suggestions of a deficiency are pointed at tackling comprehensive problems altogether. Quotations 1, 2, and 3 (Informants 2, 3, and 6) shed light on parental support with regard to inclusive education. The complex nature of family participation in the inclusive education process is illustrated by these quotations, showing the different ways.

B. Materials and Resources

This is a theme that highlights the significance of customized instructional material in a participatory classroom setup. Needs for suit work sheets are outlined in quotation (Informant 2). It highlights the demand of specific worksheets for students with the disabilities according to their needs. As argued by Quotations (Informant 5 and 9), appropriateness of instructional materials that match curriculum leads to effective teaching approaches. Call for special needs materials emphasizes more on the need of specialty resources that are designed for the unique needs.

C. Space Constraints

This illustrates how non-SPED teachers experience difficulties such as students with ASD and ADHD. Informant No. 8 focuses on Classroom Space Needs and says that space is more needed when dealing with ASD students. The same quote also refers to space constraints, indicating that the physical conditions exist, which may affect the performance of SPED learners.

D. Teacher Attributes

This highlights the unseen qualities important in building a conducive learning atmosphere. The ninth quote is about Patience Needs that highlights the role of patience and love towards creating a feeling at home for learners. This quote goes on to say that love and belonging is another way of expressing in a different form that it gives people a feeling that they are loved and matter.

The “Training and Support” theme’s findings are consistent with the integrated theoretical framework, which offers a more detailed perspective on non-SPED teacher training and support in inclusive classrooms. The significance of customized instructional materials mirrors Ainscow’s framework for inclusive education. Quotes demonstrate the importance of textbooks that are consistent with the curriculum as a part of the student-oriented approach of inclusive education. In “Space constraints”, this is where the theory of self-efficacy by Bandura comes in. Classroom Space Needs reflect the psychological issues pertaining to instruction and are influenced by a teacher’s confidence.

This was confirmed during the peer briefing that there should be a constant training for the Receiving Teachers particularly in developing lesson plans, modifying activities or worksheets, crafting instructional materials, and knowing the different teaching strategies in handling learners with special needs and having continuous training in Filipinos Sign Language from Basic to Advance level. It was also being said that the administrators like the School Heads and Master Teachers also need to have more training about Inclusive Education particularly about Learners with Disabilities for them to provide intensive Technical Assistance to the Receiving Teachers.

Overarching Theme Two: Subjective Experiences with Support, Training, and Resources

A. Support from Administration

Regular progress checks undertaken by the principals encourage a culture of openness and sharing in the school. It gives the teachers a space to talk about their experiences and difficulties too as they help to enhance the mental health of teachers which leads to a supportive school culture. The administration also demonstrates professional development through tailored training programs such as LAC for non-SPED teachers to understand and manage learners with disabilities.

These positive aspects can be attributed to the fact that the theme of limited support perception highlights some gaps in communication as well as unmet needs, calling on administrators to involve themselves in seeking the feedback to improve and address the dynamic challenges which are inherently associated with inclusive education.

B. Support from Colleagues

In the domain of inclusive education is presented as being cooperative. This focus on referencing SPED teacher's highlights that they are experts and need collectivize effort among teacher to resolve learners with special needs crisis. This is also reflected in the theme of colleagues' mutual sharing of experiences in a culture of collaboration. This is through sharing of ideas on how colleagues can deal with the students' challenges towards creation of a conducive learning environment to support educators.

C. Support from Parents

This theme is significant for the creation of a comprehensive and supportive learning environment. The fact that parents are expected to love their children and provide necessary educational material shows that, indeed, home and schoolwork in tandem. The partnership is deemed as an important element that creates a comprehensive and meaningful learning environment for these students. The parental aspect of partial support to children also comes to the forefront as the parent's collaboration with the teachers needs to be enhanced. The acknowledgement implies the need for some specific strategies which should be focused on solving the cases when parents' involvement is lacking.

D. Emotional Support and Strategy Discussion

The frequent visits of a principal in a classroom and asking a question on progress creates a situation that is suitable enough for open talk. This approach shows care and concern as the teacher shares his/her challenges in addition to creating a conducive environment that allows the teacher to open and seek guidance in the issues that are affecting the teaching and learning experience. In this context, however, the concept of leadership entails more than administration and the emotional needs of teaching children with special needs. According to the quote the strategy discussions imply a consultative approach, where the principal is involved in solving problems and providing the necessary support to non-SPED teachers working in inclusive classrooms resulting to successful inclusive teaching experiences.

These results support Social Constructivism by Vygotsky (1978) and ecological Systems Theory of Bronfenbrenner. An open culture is developed as regular progress reports are made in line with joint experiences. Training programs tailor-made as being evidence for the effect of exosystem in inclusive education. This makes it possible for constructive management support, which is pivotal for creating a culture that promotes co-construction of knowledge. This aligns with Vygotsky's concept of collaboration in learning when referring to inclusive education Shared experience and development of joint expertise between SPED teachers refers to speaking out loud, "experts".

The ecological systems theory is manifested in the concept of the mesosystem which highlights the relevance of support from parent as a key contributing factor to the practice of inclusive education. Recognizing half-support means for tactics relating to many level issues.

The aspect of "Emotional Support and Strategy Discussion" agrees with the Social Co-constructivism proposed by Vygotsky. Openness during principal visits is an indication of a collaborated experience. Therefore, this is an appropriate approach to solving problems that are collaborative in nature for the inclusive teaching environment. In summary, these data point out the social and situational factors that affect regular instruction practitioners within inclusive setting.

This was confirmed during the peer briefing that the support from their colleagues was quite evident to their respective schools since it is easier for them to communicate with each other and share their teaching experiences in inclusive class. However, with regards to support form parents, it was suggested during the discussion that the administrators may conduct training for parents in handling learners with disabilities so that they may give appropriate and continuous support to their children at home. Thus, it may lead to a good collaboration and cooperation from the parents and Receiving teachers in inclusive class.

Overarching Theme Three. Personal and Emotional Experiences of Non-SPED Teachers

A. Handling Difficulty

The topic of dealing with difficulties reveals a complex scene when examining personal and emotional backgrounds of non-SPED teachers working with diagnosed students. The first informant's acknowledgement of the intricacies presented by this teaching context, which includes acknowledging the inherent difficulties in dealing with SEN learners, underlines the complexity attached to it.

The word "somewhat" indicates a spectrum of difficulties such that, while non-SPED teachers deal with some hurdles, they can still negotiate the spectrum.

B. Emotional Stress

Non-SPED teachers have emotionally, and personally suffered. The statement "nakakastress" by the first informant and the struggle to suppress emotions reveal the complexity in a teacher's emotions in a case where he or she is dealing with diagnosed students. It emphasizes the emotional commitment on the part of generalists with SPED students and the need for effective emotional support and resources.

C. Personal Initiative

The personal initiative theme is about what non-SPED teachers can do for diagnosed students within the context of their experiences. Second informant showed commitment by personally providing resources as well as getting instructional materials from the SPED Department. The implication here is that non-SPED teachers strive to acquire relevant resources to facilitate their work.

D. Behavioral Hardships

On the other hand, the theme of behavioral hardships throws light on the difficulties that non-SPED instructors undergo in dealing with the behaviors of diagnosed students. Hardships that come with handling the pupil's behavior are indicated by the second responder. It highlights the need for non-SPED teachers to develop behavior management strategies and suggests that this requires appropriate professional development and support.

Findings in this "handling difficulty" theme perfectly match my theoretical framework which includes a social constructivist approach as proposed by Vygotsky and self-efficacy, based on the works of Bandura. This explains how social construction of knowledge occurs in relation to non-spced teachers who experience collaborative learning. In this respect, the theme "Emotional Stress" is very close to Bandura's notion of self-effectiveness and explores psychological aspects of teaching for diagnosed students. For example, use of expressions like "nakakastress" which translates as causing stress as well as struggles in suppression of emotions emphasize that non-SPED teacher must be emotionally committed thus matching into Bandura's perspective where beliefs play a big part in determining motivations and results.

"Personal Initiative" squares itself very well with both Bandura's theory and Vygotsky's Social Constructivism. The second informant self-efficacy is portrayed through show of resourcefulness and determination demonstrated in providing the required resources. That theme of "Behavioral Hardships" corresponds with Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism and Bandura theory showing difficulties on how to handle behaviorally diagnosed students. Such problems indicate that this calls for behavior management strategies and the appropriate professional development which is consistent with Vygotsky's emphasis of working together in solving issues.

Summing up these themes, it gives light to the complexity of the issues connected with the difficulties associated with inclusive classes experienced by non-SPED teachers. Personal and Emotional Experiences of Non-SPED Teachers particularly handling difficulty and emotional stress were confirmed during the peer briefing. It was discussed that the Non-SPED Teachers are having a hard time in dealing with the different behaviors of the learners with disabilities especially if they were having tantrums during class discussion.

Overarching Theme Four. Adaptation of Teaching Methods, Classroom Management, and Collaboration

A. Pedagogical Adaptation

Through this, the non-SPED teachers illustrate their commitment to pedagogical adaptation, whereby activities are adapted to the needs of the diagnosed learners (one quotation - informant 1). The second informant adopts a pedagogical teaching approach. This points to the responsiveness of the teaching processes (Quotation from Informant 2). It stresses the need to use varied learning approaches to meet the needs of both diagnosed and normal learners.

B. Classroom Management

Non-SPED teachers adopt the principle of inclusive treatment, whereby diagnosed pupils are oriented appropriately while established rules prevent disturbances and tantrums. Safe spaces are also evident within the classroom environment with informant 6 mentioning routine activities, and instruction on safety that demonstrate a reactive approach in mitigating possible challenges (quoted from Informant 6). As far as informant number 7 is concerned, the diagnosis of a learner is positioned in such a manner wherein a comfortable and productive environment is created (Quote by Informant number 7).

C. Collaboration with Colleagues

It becomes evident that open communication and collaboration with co-workers are significant aspects in adapting to the needs of identified students. They demonstrate an ability to work independently within established parameters. Open communication between the subject teacher is needed to understand behavior patterns and manage the diagnosed students (Informant 1). Quote 9 indicates that the colleagues introduce the diagnosed students, share insights from them and work together in creating strategies (Informant 9). Informant 6 goes further on extending collaboration to a departmental level where he advises fellow teachers on how to handle learners with special needs in a way that is consistent with the general approach (Quotation, Informant 6).

The "Pedagogical Adaptation" theme illustrates that other non-special education practitioner teachers agree to adjusting the activities to the necessities of diagnosed pupils, embodying what Vygotsky suggests for collective and culturally structured understanding process.

Meanwhile, "Working together with colleagues" supports Vygotsky's social constructivism and Ainscow's model by stressing the importance of an open dialogue between staff for powerful teaching strategies. Working in an independent manner within the set regulations corresponds to Ainscow's model of pupil/student-centered curriculum systems. Collaboration at the departmental level highlights that students' needs can be met through teamwork.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions were derived.

This research contributed to the field of education by finding out the challenges and difficulties of Non-SPED teachers experience when teaching learners with learning difficulties and how they attempt to overcome these situations.

This study contributed to educational management by proposing administrative support to the Non-SPED teachers particularly in conducting specialized training programs and providing resources for individualized instructional materials, worksheets, and specific resources for persons with disabilities.

In inclusive classroom, however, focused training is necessary, especially on responding adequately to the specific demands that persons with disabilities have.

Non-SPED teachers recognize some support like regularly scheduled visits by principals and Individualized Education Program (IEP) reviews; however, they consistently demand stronger administrative support in dealing with the complexities that come with inclusive education.

Together, the participants reiterate the significance of SPED teacher and colleague contributions towards their collaborative effort while discussing experiences and promoting communications systems. The multi-faceted nature of inclusive education necessitates these collaborative initiatives to help address them.

Their daily roles that evoke emotions like anger, frustration, and perpetual patient-like behavior prove very problematic. Additionally, the non-SPED teachers have demonstrated their involvement in improving their diagnosed students' education by providing resources, participating in training, and adapting their teaching approaches.

References

- Ainscow, M. (2020). Promoting inclusion and equity in education: lessons from international experiences. *Nordic Journal of Studies in Educational Policy*, 6(1), 7-16.
- Aquino, L. N., Mamat, N., & Che Mustafa, M. (2019). Levels of competence in the learning domains of kindergarten entrants. *Southeast Asia Early Childhood Journal*, 8(1), 37-45. <https://doi.org/10.37134/saecj.vol8.no1.5.2019>.
- Block, E., Breaud, M., McNulty, C., Papa, T. and Perry, M. (2019). Perspectives of special education: Literature review and interview. *Creative Education*, 10, 1973-1981. doi: 10.4236/ce.2019.109143.
- Fleming V, Gaidys, U., and Robb. Y. (2003). Hermeneutic research in nursing: developing a Gadamerian-based research method. *Nursing Inquiry* 10(2): 113–120.
- Núñez, O., & Rosales, S. (2021). Inclusive education: Perceptions and attitudes among Filipino high school teachers. Retrieved June 3, 2023 from <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?q=related:ecDAMEcr1AgJ:scholar.google.com/&scioq=regular+teacher>
- Quinones, T. (2022). Exploring Inclusive Education in the Senior High School as Bridging Program to Tertiary Career Pathing. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2 (7), 260-274. <https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/IJAMS-JULY-ISSUE-260-274.pdf>.
- Quizana, C. and Espiritu, M. (2023). Challenges encountered and coping strategies used by teachers in implementing SPED inclusive education program in public elementary schools of Third Congressional District, Division of Quezon.
- Sampaga, R. (2020). Lived experiences of special education teachers in San Fernando City sped integrated school. *GSI: Volume 10, Issue 4, April 2022 ISSN 2320-9186*.

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